

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

NATIONAL PRACTICES OF LOCAL COMMUNITY HEALTH PROGRAMMES IMPLEMENTATION IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

As a result of the growing state budget deficit and constant underfunding, Ukraine's healthcare system faces the need for rapid reform. Gradual changes in the principles of organisation, accountability, and other aspects of the system began in 2016, and its effectiveness is beyond doubt. However, there are still issues related to the planning, implementation and evaluation of relevant healthcare programmes, especially at the local level, which is an important part of the healthcare financing system. The article analyses the current state of affairs and international experience related to the organisation of healthcare financing reforms at the local level. This process was based on the investigation of local healthcare care financing programmes in three regions and data from a survey of representatives of local governments and healthcare institutions. The study showed the need to ensure participatory processes in the organisation of health care financing at the community level; further digitalisation of all aspects of local government and health care institutions; and more effective use of key performance indicators to verify the success of programme implementation. This set of recommendations will accelerate the transformation process and strengthen the capacity of the Ukrainian healthcare system.

Keywords: healthcare, local administration, health care institutions

Introduction.

Since the early 2000s, according to available statistics [17], the healthcare sector has been underfunded due to the state budget deficit. With the global crisis of 2007–2008, the situation deteriorated significantly and reached its peak in 2013. These processes had a negative impact on the healthcare sector. Among the most negative factors that affected the development of the industry are:

- high degree of bureaucratization [3]
- low salaries for highly qualified employees, which were significantly lower in purchasing power than in any other European country [16];
- a significant level of corruption among industry management, as evidenced by several corruption scandals [1];
- insufficient material and technical support from health care institutions [2];
- lack of modern regulation of treatment procedures and outdated organisational structure [2].

These reasons and the overcoming of the main consequences of the political crisis provoked by the Russian Federation in 2013 and 2014 revoke a comprehensive reform of the Ukrainian health care system. In the course of this reform, the system changed from medical subventions to payment under Medical Guarantee Programme (MGP) contracts concluded with the National Health Service of Ukraine (NHSU), the sole purchaser of medical services. To be eligible to enter

into contracts as MGPs, municipal healthcare institutions (MHI) had to change their ownership from budgetary institutions to municipal non-profit enterprises (MNE).

As part of healthcare reform, the role and responsibilities of local governments (LGEs), the owners of healthcare facilities (HCFs), have also changed. According to the reform plan, LGEs were to focus on building an effective healthcare network, managing healthcare facilities, seeking additional funding from various sources (grants, international assistance, private investors, etc.) and using opportunities for inter-municipal cooperation in the sector.

Furthermore, the reform aimed to gradually digitalise the sector, which would reduce bureaucracy and strengthen control over the use of earmarked funds.

The implemented accounting, reporting, and control system allows tracking how funds are allocated to finance services and what specific services are provided to patients. However, local sources also play an important role in financing healthcare facilities. However, funding from local resources is not always subject to the same level of control and regulation. Sometimes this process is determined by non-transparent principles and may not always take into account maximising the efficiency and quality of healthcare services.

The analysis of available information gives grounds to raise the issue of efficiency of spending available financial and other resources. Often, local government funds distribution is based on criteria other

than efficiency [9]. At the same time, when developing regional programmes, key performance indicators and programme analysis can be neglected. As a result, such programmes do not fully utilise the means to solve targeted problems and do not contribute to increasing public confidence in the system as a whole.

The situation has only deteriorated since the start of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by the Russian Federation. The emotional perception of this state of affairs by the population caused an increase in the number of new diseases and, therefore, pressure on health care facilities [8]. This, in turn, led to exposure to the ineffectiveness of reforms at the local level, which, in combination with other factors, including migration, led to deterioration in the provision of health care services. Therefore, it can be assumed that studying the state of affairs and identifying the largest gaps in the development of health programmes at the local level is one of the components to improve the overall efficiency of the processes for the formation of an effective health care system. Solving this task would improve the quality of services provided and, consequently, reduce the level of public distrust in the system, which is a particularly acute problem during the war.

The current article analyses existing practices and approaches to regional healthcare budgeting in the Kyiv, Zhytomyr and Chernihiv regions in order to identify the most acute gaps and improve the planning, implementation, and evaluation of regional healthcare programmes. Best international practices were also studied, including results-based budgeting; financial sustainability indicators; international benchmarks, etc. – and recommendations applicable to the Ukrainian context were identified.

Methodology.

The financing of healthcare institutions is regulated by the current legislation of Ukraine, which regulates the process of financing healthcare expenditures. According to the Ukrainian Budget Code, such expenditures can be divided into 3 levels, each of which has its own target areas:

1. Expenditures made from the State Budget of Ukraine:

- programmes that ensure the implementation of national functions, according to the list approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine;
- state public health programmes and measures to combat epidemics;
- state programmes for the development and support of state-owned health facilities;
- state programmes and measures in the field of health care implemented by state institutions.

2. Expenditures made from the budgets of village, town and city territorial communities;

- payment for utilities and energy resources of municipal healthcare facilities owned by the respective territorial communities to ensure the provision of healthcare services under the PFM;
- local programmes for the development and support of municipal healthcare facilities;
- local public health programmes.

3. Expenditures made from the budget of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and regional budgets:

- payment for utilities and energy for municipal HCFs;
- regional programmes for the development and support of municipal healthcare facilities;
- support of other institutions in the healthcare system (orphanages, blood service institutions, medical and social expert commissions, forensic bureaus, special medical supply bases).

As already mentioned, the current article focusses on the second level – expenditures made from the budgets of village, town, and city territorial communities.

To conduct a comprehensive analysis of existing practices and approaches to regional budgeting in the health care sector, qualitative data and information on all aspects of financing health care programmes and activities at the local level were collected. The main ways of collecting this data were the following:

- analysis of open sources of information (websites of local governments, health care facilities, the State Statistics Service, etc.);
- written requests to local self-government bodies;
- self-completion of data collection forms by responsible employees of local governments and healthcare facilities with the advisory support of experts (to facilitate the collection process, an online survey was conducted).

The data obtained were verified by means of logical control and spot check. And the analysis process itself was carried out according to agreed approaches and using standard statistical methods.

The first two areas of data collection allowed for a comparative analysis of the financial and programmatic indicators of selected local health programmes in 2020-2023. For this purpose, budget programme passports for the selected period and relevant implementation reports were collected and analysed.

In addition, a survey was conducted using a form that contained 126 questions and focused on the following aspects of local government activities:

- organisational structure and other executive aspects related to the implementation and support of healthcare care programmes.
- completeness of the preliminary analysis of the legal acts regulating the relevant programmes and the creation of their local counterparts;
- the extent to which various indicators are taken into account when developing a local health care programme;
- the nature of the assessment of the necessary resources for programme implementation;
- peculiarities of drawing conclusions and assessing the quality of implementation of relevant programmes.

The survey process itself focused on two groups of respondents: representatives of local governments involved in the development of the health care system in communities and representatives of health care institutions.

Eight countries were selected as a basis to compare the effectiveness of local health programmes: Can-

ada, Georgia, Poland, Rwanda, Spain, Sweden, Thailand, and the United Kingdom. The list was generated based on the following criteria:

- countries in which the creation and management of the health care system differs from the Soviet model at the central/national, regional, territorial and / or municipal / local levels;
- countries with a geopolitical history to Ukraine and their health care system is part of the former Soviet system (Georgia and Poland);
- countries that have rebuilt their health care system after a conflict or serious economic crisis (Canada, Rwanda, Thailand, and the United Kingdom).

In terms of planning local health programmes, the following indicators were identified:

- country context;
- relationship with national and local programmes;
- evaluation of resources required for implementation (financial, labour, etc.);
- the process of involving health care providers in the planning process;
- public consultations;
- list of implementers;
- sources of funding
- key performance indicators.

Regarding the stage of implementation of local healthcare programmes, the following characteristics were analysed:

- context;
- coordination of implementation (i.e., monthly, quarterly meetings, reporting);
- monitoring of implementation;
- mitigation of implementation risks and unforeseen circumstances;
- public participation.

Regarding the stage of evaluation of the implementation of local health care programmes, the following features were determined:

- public participation;
- mitigation of programme risks and contingencies;
- key performance indicators (KPIs) compared to benchmarks and to baselines;
- budget cycle implications (how results are transformed into a new budget cycle);
- implications for financial year planning (how the monitoring and evaluation indicators of achievement/non-achievement affect budgeting and planning for the next financial year);
- stakeholder accountability.

A variety of open data sources were used to conduct a literature review of international best practices for specific countries and local health programmes. PubMed, Google Scholar, the Global Health Library, the World Health Organisation library database, and the Intergovernmental Organisation search engine.

Main Part.

The first stage of the comprehensive analysis, as part of the ongoing work, was to evaluate the results of a survey of representatives of local governments and healthcare facilities. The study, which included a survey of local self-government bodies, found that some executive bodies of local councils, especially in small communities, lack specialised departments that deal with the support of health development. Therefore, it is common practice that the work of preparing healthcare projects is actually delegated to the management of the relevant institution.

There are not always specific persons who are responsible for the development, implementation and evaluation of local health programmes. In some cases, programme developers are representatives of financial departments who are not deeply involved in health care issues. This state of affairs significantly complicated the data collection in the survey and narrowed the range of potential respondents. Additionally, some representatives of local governments refused to participate in the survey due to time constraints, high workloads in their workplaces, lack of staff to delegate this task, and the large size of the questionnaire. A total of 25 respondents responded to the questionnaire, characterised by the following distribution by institution and region, as shown in Figures 1.a and 1.b, respectively.

Despite the above, out of the 25 respondents, only one village council reported that it did not participate in the development of local health programmes. Therefore, it can be argued that health programmes are comprehensive and that there is a high level of community involvement in their development.

Having reviewed the main features, a gradual overview of the survey results according to its key elements can be provided. The first important part is the organisational structure and other executive aspects.

For the vast majority of professionals, work with local health programmes is included in their job descriptions (84 % of respondents), and 44 % of respondents have received additional training in developing such programmes. Furthermore, the educational level of the respondents is high, as almost all of them have higher education (sometimes two or three). The predominant fields of study are medicine, public management and administration, economics, law, etc.

Figure 1 – Distribution of respondents

Source: Author's calculations

At the same time, the organisation of the development process is most often carried out through the creation of a relevant working group (60 % of cases), which ensures the participation of various participants, the distribution of responsibilities, and the creation of conditions for the publicity of the process. Among the respondents, only one city council has a health department as the main programme developer. In 40 % of cases, a working group is not created, which actually means a departure from the project-based principles of organising activities.

It should be noted that only a third of the respondents participate in the working groups. At the same time, public consultations and the opportunity to submit a proposal to the list of activities of the local health programme remain the main tools of engagement. 13% of

the respondents said that the public is not involved at all.

A deeper analysis of the respondents' understanding of "involvement" showed that in the vast majority of cases, the "public" is understood to mean deputies and other representatives related to the area of their main activity. Only in 20 % of cases, it refers to public hearings, questionnaires, and surveys of the population, and other similar mechanisms. At the same time, the results indicate (Figure 2) that the effectiveness of such engagement is insufficient. None of the respondents gave the highest score to the effectiveness of public participation in the process of developing a local programme.

Figure 2 – Self-assessment of the effectiveness of public participation in the health programme development process (in points, where 5 is the highest score)

Source: Author's calculations

HCFs mostly initiate requests for development of local programmes on their own, and only in 20 % of cases, the requests are made by LGEs. At the same time, the overwhelming majority of respondents stated that LGEs send requests to HCFs to identify additional funding.

The next aspect on which the survey focused was the regulatory framework for the development of programme documents to finance the development of healthcare facilities.

The survey showed that there is a significant gap in the development of the regulatory framework for local health care programmes. Most (60 %) communities lack local regulations that describe the procedures and processes for planning and implementing targeted pro-

grammes. 40 % of respondents indicated the availability of acts describing procedures, deadlines for each stage, implementers, and the form of the local programme and relevant indicators, but this is a generalised document without defining the specifics of budget planning processes for this area.

The third important part is the degree to which performance indicators are taken into account in the development of local health programmes. Among the list of amalgamated community indicators used as benchmarks in the development of targeted programmes, demographic, socioeconomic, medical and statistical indicators play an important role, with somewhat less attention paid to epidemic surveillance and public health indicators (Figure 3).

Figure 3 – Consideration of additional indicators in programme development (% of respondents)
 Source: Author’s calculations

Among the communities analysed, the most frequently allocated expenditures are for diagnosing and treating tuberculosis patients among children and adults. Furthermore, in 2020-2021, some communities allocated funds for payments related to the prevention of the spread of COVID-19 coronavirus infection. In general, the results of the survey showed that the process of analysing additional indicators in the development of a local health programme in the community is implemented in half of the cases by representatives of local authorities and in the other half of the cases by the management of health care facilities.

It should be emphasised that in the process of programme development, the draught financial plans of the HCF for the planning period and/or the results of the implementation of financial plans of previous periods are analysed (88 % of respondents). This, in turn, affects the next, fourth, important part of the healthcare programming process identified by the survey, the nature of the evaluation of the necessary resources for the implementation of the programme.

Most of the resource needs are determined jointly by the HCF and the LGA, primarily, this concerns financial and material resources, but in some cases the

HCFs determine the human, intellectual, and technological indicators independently. On the basis of the above, it is natural that the planning of local programme resource indicators is based on a retrospective approach, when the amount of resources required is determined based on the data of previous periods. The practice of focussing on requests from health care facilities is also widespread (4-10 %). When justifying decisions, it is common to use the experience of other communities (Figure 4).

Preparation of information on the need for capital expenditures for the development of a local community health programme is carried out at the request of the health care facility, which is pre-agreed with the LGA, but during the military conflict these processes are limited due to the priority of allocating funds for military needs.

The final element of the evaluation was to determine the specifics of the conclusions and to assess the quality of the implementation of the relevant programmes.

Figure 4 – Decision-making factors for resource provision (% of respondents)
 Source: Author’s calculations

In general, 84 % of the respondents noted that four groups of indicators (cost, product, efficiency, and quality indicators) are used to assess performance. The remaining 16 % emphasise that such an assessment is carried out by separate groups of performance indicators depending on the intended purpose. As a rule, two or three groups are used in such cases. It is important to note that in 80 % of cases, no barriers and risks of non-compliance is conducted. Only one respondent noted that in the process of developing programmes, they identify and assess ways to overcome key risks of their implementation.

In the process of implementing local healthcare programmes, 87 % of the cases represent the responsible implementer, that is, the healthcare facility, analyses the state of resource use. However, it is worth noting that in some programmes both the HCF and the LGA are indicated as the responsible executor, which leads to blurring of responsibility and violation of the principle of unity of authority. No respondent mentioned the participation of best practices and the analysis of their resource support.

Regarding key performance indicators, their assessment is generally carried out by the administration of the HCF or a specialised structural unit of the LGA (92 % of respondents). Among the information sources used for the evaluation, the primary statistical data of the HCF prevail (60 % of respondents), while the practice of using data from the NHSU and other institutions is less common.

Analysis of reports related to the implementation of targeted programmes revealed that only two communities have detailed information on the implementation or reasons for the failure to implement each measure in their reports on the results of local health programmes. In several other communities, reports formally state that a measure has been implemented or provide little or no explanation as to why it has not been implemented. In one community, a report on the Programme for the Development and Financing of Healthcare Facilities and the Programme for the Purchase of Housing for Medical Workers is provided in the Plan for the Socioeconomic Development of the Territorial Community. In most cases, however, communities publish only reports on the implementation of budget-programme passports.

In general, when approving local healthcare care programmes, almost all LGEs specify a specific amount of planned funding for programme implementation. In some cases, the amount of funding is replaced by the phrase "within financial capacities", which makes it impossible to analyse.

Items of planned expenditures in local health programmes can be conditionally divided into two groups with respective branches:

1. Traditional areas of funding:
 - payment for utilities;
 - purchase of equipment;
 - procurement of medicines;
 - procurement of medical devices;
 - purchase of vehicles;
 - improvement of medical infrastructure;
 - capital expenditures for healthcare facilities;

- salaries and wages.
- 2. Other areas of funding:
 - prevention of the spread of infectious and viral diseases;
 - dental services;
 - support and preservation of human resources in healthcare institutions;
 - measures related to martial law;
 - subventions;
 - covering the costs of providing medical services to the population;
 - payment for services other than utilities;
 - purchase of food.

An important factor that is taken into account when planning further programmes is overcoming the consequences of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by the Russian Federation. Since its inception, 186 health facilities have been destroyed and 1409 damaged, of which 335 have been fully restored and another 355 partially restored.

Most institutions are restored at the expense of the state budget, international grant organisations, and charitable foundations, and less often at the expense of the local budget and the own resources of institutions that are financially capable. The results of the analysis of local health care programmes confirm this thesis, as most of them do not include funds for postwar recovery, meeting the health care needs of military personnel or internally displaced people, or equipping facilities with proper shelters.

Regarding the performance indicators, based on the analysis of the reports, it can be concluded that they are practically absent from local programmes. In the development stage, only two communities include performance indicators in their programme passports. At the same time, only in one case, among quality indicators, is an indicator as the percentage of patients satisfied with the medical services received in city hospitals and outpatient general practice clinics indicated and measured. In 2022, due to martial law, this survey was not conducted. In all other communities, performance indicators are provided in the Passports of Budget Programmes, as required by the form to fill out this type of document.

An important factor for understanding the context is the analysis of the execution of the local budget. For example, in the Zhytomyr region, the regional programme "Health of the Zhytomyr Region Population" has been implemented in the healthcare sector in recent years. Thus, in 2021, UAH 227.9 billion were allocated from the local budgets of the Zhytomyr region for the development of health care, and 98.8 % of the planned funding was actually spent. In 2022, the planned amount of funding for the healthcare sector increased by UAH 23.8 billion compared to 2021 and totalled UAH 251.7 billion. In 2022, the plan was fulfilled by 98.4 %.

On August 1, 2023, UAH 119.7 billion was allocated from the local budgets of the Zhytomyr region to support the development of the healthcare sector, which is equal to 47.1 % of the planned funding for this sector, UAH 254.2 billion. The graphical interpretation of the results is shown in Figure 5.

On the basis of the above data, it can be stated that due to the budget deficit at the local level, the amount planned in the programme is not realised. At the same time, the percentage of unused funds is gradually increasing. A similar situation is also observed in Kyiv region [11] and Chernihiv region [15]. In each case, there is an increase in healthcare expenditures in hryvnia and percentage terms relative to the total regional budget. This is due to the burden of all healthcare sec-

tors caused by hostilities and inflation. It is worth noting that, given the circumstances, a similar situation with increased expenditures is likely to be observed in 2024.

The final step of the analysis, according to the defined methodology, was a study of international experience. It was used to formulate a set of the most important recommendations aimed at planning, implementing and evaluating health care programmes.

Figure 5 – Structure of local budget expenditures on health care in Zhytomyr region

Source: Department of Health Protection of the Zhytomyr Regional State Administration [6]

For the planning stage, given the peculiarities of the Ukrainian context, it is necessary to take into account

- the importance of integrating local programmes with national health goals and programmes. This practice has become widespread with the recent health care reform in the UK. This allows reducing the level of bureaucracy and, at the same time, increasing the consistency of all local programmes [5];

- establishing authorised regional health teams that are well informed and strengthened to perform various responsibilities. In the context of Ukraine, there is a centralised institution that monitors the reform process in all regions, but as the UK experience shows, regionalism is an important factor for proper planning of health programmes. This is due to both social and geographical factors [5];

- the local level to determine the health care needs of the population. This is in part inherent in the process of planning health care programmes in Ukraine. However, according to the survey, this is not in line with international practice, which is reflected in the health care systems of different European countries [7, 13];

- regional authorities should supervise the activities of regional health care systems, coordinate, and manage the procurement of health care services for their region. According to the survey, in some cases, especially for small communities, the actual developer of the programme is the HCF. Poland's experience

shows that in such cases, supervision should be carried out by regional authorities. This, as well as the first recommendation, is the consistency of all local programmes [12];

- each HCF should be responsible for human resources management, supplies, financial resources, and staff training, and coordinate inter-sectoral cooperation with other departments (e.g., social welfare and agriculture), if necessary. The reform of the health system in Rwanda has shown that health facilities, despite the constant supervision of regional authorities, should retain some autonomy in certain stages of planning [10].

For the implementation stage, the following important recommendations can be identified based on international experience.

- the importance of informing the population about the programme, its goals, benefits, and ways to participate, which will promote more active citizen engagement and increase the chances of the programme's success. Sweden's experience has shown that the public, in addition to basic oversight, can create additional ideas and concepts that will improve the process of implementing health programmes at the local level. This also increases the general level of public trust in the system [13]. This information can be provided through annual public hearings, which have proven effective in Thailand [14].

- develop a detailed financial plan for the programme. Given the number of health care reforms in

Europe, a highly detailed financial plan, taking into account emergency circumstances (pandemic, military conflicts, migration crises, etc.) is one of the fundamental steps to ensure the effectiveness of the implementation phase. For Ukraine, this recommendation is a particular priority, given the military-political and economic context [7, 13];

The following recommendations can be made for the evaluation stage.

- engage independent experts to evaluate programme implementation. This helps to obtain an objective assessment and recommendations for further development and is a common practice in all European countries. In Ukraine, such participation is provided, but not mandatory, which, based on the results of the survey, can negatively affect the results of implementation [7, 13];

- organisation of operational planning, resource allocation, procurement, and provision at the local level (regional health authorities). In addition to engaging external experts, it is important to establish local bodies that would be directly responsible for responding promptly to changes caused by emergencies. The same organisations should also conduct an interim evaluation of the implementation to determine the need for intervention. This practice is typical for the Spanish healthcare system [4].

- establish feedback mechanisms for timely reporting of policies and management responses to all stakeholders and publicising such issues. This recommendation is a logical continuation of the thesis presented for the implementation stage. The experience of Thailand and some European countries has shown that this allows one to achieve the required level of transparency and public control [7, 13, 14].

Findings.

The study analysed the planning, implementation and evaluation processes of health programmes at the local level. Based on this analysis, a set of recommendations can be established for the planning, implementation and evaluation of local health programmes. In particular,

- ensuring the most transparent and understandable process of formulating and discussing programmes, as well as regular reporting and publication of performance evaluation;

- clearly defining the goals to be achieved by the local programme, which will help to identify specific, measurable, and achievable expected results;

- determining the list of responsible executors after discussions with all stakeholders and key performance indicators, including a comprehensive analysis and forecasting of resources;

- promoting practices of sharing responsibility for the implementation of programme activities, including joint implementation of activities by HCFs and MHIs with the participation of the public and healthcare professionals;

- application of the latest technological solutions, in particular the introduction of electronic health systems, telemedicine, and other technological tools, can improve the quality of service and reduce the bureaucracy of many processes;

- engaging external experts to conduct an independent assessment of the local programme by specialists, which can provide an objective assessment of the results achieved and suggest areas for improvement;

- regular feedback from patients on their satisfaction with the medical care they received, the quality and accessibility of medical care in the community, practices of informal and out-of-pocket payments for services guaranteed by the state, and the need to introduce new medical and nonmedical services,

If these recommendations are taken into account, the process of implementing healthcare programmes can become much more efficient, both from a financial and social point of view.

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